

THE IMPORTANCE OF "BOYSUN MAVRIGI" DANCE IN THE FORMATION OF SURKHAN DANCE SCHOOL.

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Abstract: In this article, the history of Surkhan valley's dance art, which is a part of Uzbek national dance art, and local aspects related to it are interpreted.

Key words: dance, art, history, style, music, melody, song, creation, mavrigi, kur, utov, jazava.

Introduction: Since the development of the art of dance is directly related to the history of the nation that created it, it is permissible to dwell on its reflection in the history of the art of dance. After all, until now, Khorezm, Bukhara and Fergana dance schools, which had their own style, were recognized in Uzbek dance art. Today, "Surkhan Dance School" has been added to the list of Uzbek dance schools. The fact that the Surkhan oasis in the south of Uzbekistan is one of the areas that has been the cradle of mankind since ancient times is evidenced by the skull of a Neanderthal child found in the Teshiktosh cave, which is considered to be the settlement of Neanderthal people belonging to the Stone Age in the village of Machai, Boysun district, and the pictures drawn by primitive people on the rocks in the Zarautsoy gorge.

Art historian Lyubov Avdeeva writes in her book "From the history of Uzbek national dance" that "Dance is an art that exists in time and space, in which an artistic image is created by rhythmically organized pictorial and expressive movements of the human body." Dance is not an art specific to one nation, but is a product of universal artistic creativity, and is an art form characteristic of all nations of the world. He created full-fledged dance art only when he felt the need to express the

beauty of human life, his place in this wide world, his feelings, subtle feelings, philosophical games with body movements. This mysterious need has become a part of human life.

"Boysun mavrigi" dance is of special importance in Surkhan dance school. This dance is completely different from other dances in its structure, movements, content and appearance. The "Mavrigi" dance is usually performed by a single dancer in the middle of the circle. During the dance, the participants of the circle also took an active part, cheering and applauding the actions of the dancer in the middle. In any ceremony, a single dancer is surrounded by seven or nine young men kneeling in a circle. They called this period "build". The fact that there are exactly seven or nine young men in the wolf is probably due to the fact that the number "7" was understood as a protection from calamities, and the number "9" as a bringer of happiness.

In the "Mavrigi" dance, special respect is shown to the solo dancer. Because, since long ago, in the territory of Surkhan oasis, if a man did not make a name for himself with some quality, bravery, he was not allowed to go out and dance at weddings and ceremonies. This custom was preserved in the mountainous villages of Boysun, Oltinsoy, Denov, and Sariosia districts of the Surkhan oasis until the 1960s.

The "Mavrigi" dance is considered the most perfect of the "jazava" dances. The peculiarity of this dance is that the whole body dances according to the method due to the "lekshima" movement of the legs in it, which is not found in other male dances. This dance is very ancient, and one of the performers known to us was Azim Surnay, who lived in the village of "Avlot" of Boysun district. Until the 60s of the 20th century, grandfather Haji Bolta, who lived in Boisun, performed this dance to its standard.

Until the 80s of the 20th century, the "Mavrigi" dance was performed by Ahad Boltaev, the son of grandfather Khoji Bolta, an excellent teacher, Zikrullo Umarov and Abdukhalil Nazarov, who was a pedagogue.

From 1986 to the present day, this dance has been performed by "Boysun" folklore-

Habib Umarov, Komil Rahmonov and Ismail Jumaev, participants of ethnographic ensemble, are performing.

"Mavrigi" is a perfect melody performed by a group of mashshoks, accompanied by a circle, flute, gijjak, rubob, dutor, and two other circles and a trumpet. In general, the performance of the "Maurigi" dance is quite different from other regions.

The difference between Boysun mavrigi dance and other masculine dances is that during the performance of this dance, the dancer relaxes all the muscles in his body without strengthening them. In addition to the precise performance of the dance movements, the body part, especially the chest and shoulders, vibrate between beats. The dancer's head should be swaying separately, and the face should have a thoughtful and serious expression until the dance begins and ends. It seems as if the whole world is moving together with the dancer, and the dancer should be listening to his inner world.

Boysun's tune "Maurigi" also has a power that restrains unruly emotions. When the melody is played in rhythm, circle beats are accented every second beat. While the dancer's movement is gentle in the first count, the dancer moves sharply at the end of the second count. In general, all the movements in the dance "Boysun Mavrigi" are performed in two contradictory numbers.

It is clear that "Boysun Moor" has been preserved intact since ancient times. This can be understood from the fact that this dance was performed in ancient ceremonies and that there is an interpretation of the connection of man with the divine forces in heaven and earth, based on the movements, gestures in the movements, and the dancer's maintaining a serious facial expression during the performance.

In ancient times, every movement, every gesture expressed concepts that could be understood by the audience even without words. That is, the role of

movement and gesture was very actively involved in the expression of thought. "Mavrigi", a masterpiece of ancient dance art, is performed as a one-man show and is still performed at weddings and festivals in Boisun.

In order to study dances of the Surkhandarya region, it is necessary to organize folklore expeditions on a large scale throughout the Oasis;

- it is necessary to study the scientific literature and manuscripts created to date on the topic and publish scientific articles and sources based on the results; - It is necessary to study and analyze the repertoire of folklore ethnographic groups existing in Surkhandarya;

In the course of the expedition organized in Surkhandarya, conducting conversations with Surkhan connoisseurs and representatives of the older generation who know national games and dances. Publication of scientific articles on the results;

- it is desirable to process the collected materials, to describe in writing the description of the specific choreographic movements of the seasonal dances, to analyze, classify, and to clarify the basics of the Surkhan school based on the results.

Summary

The rich and colorful folklore heritage of the people of Uzbekistan is closely related to the diversity of its ethnic composition and the fact that the path of historical development passed between two rivers in Central Asia, one of the centers of world civilization. Because the area between Amudarya and Syrdarya served as a crossroad in the great migrations of peoples and the rise and development of various political, cultural and economic relations since ancient times. Only Great in this regard

It is enough to remember that the silkworm almost completely crosses this area. On the other hand, it is natural that economic, political and cultural development took place wherever the trade routes passed.

In conclusion, studying and analyzing the dances of the Surkhan dance school, teaching the masterpieces of our national dance art to the younger generation, and

thus passing on our national intangible cultural heritage to future generations, remains one of the good and responsible tasks facing music experts.

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